

HISTORY OF EMERGENCE OF TELEVISION ART

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684594>

Abstract. *This article talks about the main directions of the discovery, history and theory of television, as well as the director's work processes.*

Key word: *television, radio, image, show, technique, studio.*

ИСТОРИЯ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ ТЕЛЕВИЗИОННОГО ИСКУССТВА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассказывается об основных направлениях открытия, истории и теории телевидения, а также о процессах работы режиссера.*

Ключевые слова: *телевидение, радио, имидж, шоу, техника, студия.*

The role of television and radio in human life is incomparable. Mass media, like all periods of human history, have been playing an important role in the development of society, in particular, in human life. It is impossible to imagine a person's life without the Internet, regardless of its type - radio and television, newspapers and magazines. The mass media informs about the events happening in the world at any time, everywhere, and affects the minds and spiritual world of people.

Television is derived from the Greek words "tele" - far, "videnie" - to see, and means to show and see action at a great distance. It should be noted with pride that Uzbekistan is the homeland of television. In 1928, the inventors Boris Pavlovich Grabovsky and Ivan Filippovich Belyansky in the house of Hamzakhan and Yusufkhan aka Mirzamuhamedov from Tashkent in the neighborhood "Balandmasjid" 74 (later Navoi Street 199) created an apparatus that transmits a moving image from one place and receives it in another place using electric light. - they invented "telephone" and successfully tested it. In Uzbekistan, television programs were officially broadcast on November 5, 1956. "Tashkent Television Studio" was established this year. This studio broadcasts its programs through the 180 m high Tashkent television tower. The first creative director Mirsolih Miragzamov, technical director Marziya Abdullayeva, director Bobo Khojaye, cameraman Polat Rasulov, first announcers were Iqbol Olimjonova, Yunona Stolyarova, Rano Madrakhimova. In 1957, the Tashkent television studio began to regularly show TV programs for 2-2.5 hours a day. In 1958, for the first time, with the help of KTS (portable television station), it

was possible to broadcast TV programs from the scene of the accident, factory and factory workshops, agricultural fields and farms, scientific laboratories and other places.

Since 1959, the range of broadcasts of the Tashkent TV Center has expanded. This year, the possibilities of delivering programs to the residents of Samarkand city, and to the residents of the large area of Bukhara and Navoi regions in 1960, were expanded. In 1961, a telecenter was launched in the city of Urganch (Khorazm region). In 1962, the second Republican program of Uzbekistan television started working. In 1962, the decision of the Supreme Soviet of Uzbekistan was made that the Telecenter was transferred from the Ministry of Communications of the Republic to the State Committee of Television and Radio Broadcasting. In 1964, a local TV studio started working in the city of Nukus (Republic of Karakalpakstan). Since 1965, it has been able to receive programs of the 1st program (ST-1) of the Central Television of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Television of Uzbekistan began to broadcast television programs through 3 programs. Since 1979, Uzbek television has had the opportunity to receive programs of the 2nd program (ST-2) of the Central Television, a total of

He started showing TV shows through 4 programs. In 1970, an independent studio "Uzbektefilm" was established on the base of Uzbekistan Television, which produces television feature and documentary films and film-concerts. In 1971, the technical and creative capabilities of the Tashkent telecenter expanded even more. In the same year, the Telecenter switched to the production of television programs in color.

1978. Preparation of programs in color image and a new television technical center for broadcasting was launched. Telecenter "Perspective" model 3rd generation.

The studio is equipped with modern television equipment, and its content is 300 sq.m. meters and 600 sq. 2 meter studios, 2 hardware-studio blocks (ASB), hardware-program blocks (APB) for broadcasting TV programs, tape recorders, mobile video and sound recording stations (KTS). The possibilities of the television of Uzbekistan have increased thanks to the new telecenter launched in 1980 and the multi-program broadcasting station installed in 1985. The height of the new TV tower is 375 meters, which doubled the broadcasting of the Tashkent TV Center. As a result, the quality of video signals improved and the number of TV shows increased. By this time, television equipment from Sony was purchased to develop the technical base. By 1990, 98 percent of the population of the republic had the opportunity to watch television programs in two programs.

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